

Application of the Capital Approach to Compute Flood Hazard, Vulnerability, and Risk at the Sub-district Level of Rajshahi Division of Bangladesh.

Aditya Dev*¹, Shamail Reza², Anisul Haque³

¹Graduate Student, Institute of Water and Flood Management, BUET, Bangladesh (adityadevami@gmail.com)

²Graduate Student, Institute of Water and Flood Management, BUET, Bangladesh (rezashamail@gmail.com)

³Professor, Institute of Water and Flood Management, BUET, Bangladesh (anisulbuet@gmail.com)

***Corresponding author**

Abstract

Floods are considered one of the most frequent and destructive disasters in Bangladesh, damaging infrastructure, human lifestyle, and social and economic status in general. In the Rajshahi Division of Bangladesh, the study focuses on how flood risk is affected by the lack of natural, human, physical, social, and financial capital at the sub-district level between 2011 and 2021. The analyses combine hydrological data and geospatial methods with other socioeconomic indicators to generate the risk, vulnerability, and hazard maps for informed decision-making and disaster management. The most crucial inputs for this analysis are the capital indices, population density, and water level statistics. The capital approach shows how geographically focused approaches can change the circumstances of flood risk. Indeed, such approaches help to build a more resilient and equitable flood management system by comparing incidence in differences in capital availability in specific areas. It has been identified that location-wise risk varies. In the study, it is found that the Singra sub-district is the lowest flood-risk-prone zone. The study implores open and collaborative approaches to disaster management, which promote initiatives that mitigate inequalities and facilitate sustainable development in Bangladesh's flood-prone regions. The results also show that the capital approach is a novel framework for risk analysis and suggest risk reduction measures for policymakers and disaster management authorities.

Keywords: capital approach; risk calculation; vulnerability assessment; flood; sub-district;

1 Introduction

Capital approaches, as frameworks for flood risk reduction, would be the strategy that policymakers and disaster management authorities approve for taking action. The methodology of capital analysis assigns point-based values to each capital (Elizondo, 2015). The flood risk is a function of the flood hazard, the exposed values, and their vulnerability. Bangladesh is internationally recognized as a flood-prone country. The climate-change-induced seasonal monsoon rainfall, upstream flow, and sea-level rise (Gain & Hoque, 2012) make the area vulnerable to severe flooding. In addition to climatic changes, unplanned economic development, significant population pressure, rapid urbanization, and land-use changes, poor governance is responsible for increased flood risk in Bangladesh (Gain & Hoque, 2012). Considering both climate-change-induced hydrologic extreme events and socioeconomic conditions, the integrated methods of flood risk assessment are required (Gain et al., 2015). Rajshahi division has long been an important hub for trade and culture in the area due to its advantageous location along the Padma River (Barcik, 2025). In Rajshahi Division, floods and droughts are frequent natural occurrences that have a substantial impact on the area's environment, economy, and residents' quality of life. There is still a lack of extensive research on this subject at the regional level. Addressing this gap is crucial for enhancing disaster risk mitigation and building resilience, as it helps to identify unique vulnerabilities within each upzillas (Azid & Alam, 2025). In areas such as the Natore district and Chapai Nababganj district of Bangladesh, where monsoon-induced riverine flooding is common, it becomes very important to assess flood hazards, vulnerabilities, and risks for informed decision-making and effective disaster management. This study intends to develop hazard, vulnerability, and risk maps for 10 subdistricts (upzillas) of the Rajshahi Division to study comprehensively their

effects on flood events. Here, geospatial methods and hydrological data are used to characterize flood-prone areas and identify different zones in terms of flood hazard intensity. The socioeconomic aspect is taken into account for assessing vulnerability levels of the population and assets to impacts caused by the flooding. Among the different approaches to computing vulnerabilities, the capital approach has been used. In the capital approach, it is assumed that changes in capital may change the vulnerability and thus may change the risk of a particular area. Risk maps are generated in ArcGIS by integrating exposure, hazard, and vulnerability layers and contribute to understanding the vulnerabilities regarding possible scenarios. Vulnerability refers to the traits and conditions of a community, system, or asset that render it vulnerable to the harmful impacts of a hazard (Kader et al., 2023). It is essential to build a community's capacity to understand its vulnerabilities, strategies, activities, and the role they could play in managing flood risks without relying on external entities (Osti et al., 2008). So, the objective of the study is to find the very high-risk prone zone from the 10 subdistricts and also apply an arbitrary change in its capital, to monitor the shifting of the risk score.

2 Study Area

Rajshahi division, with 18,153.08 sq km (Wikipedia, 2025), is one of the largest divisions in Bangladesh (24°22'26.40" N, 88°36'4.10" E.) (Wikipedia, 2025). From this broader division, among 8 districts, Natore district and Chapai Nababganj district have been selected for study to see the risk variation because Natore district is situated in the center of Rajshahi division, and on the other hand, Chapai Nawabganj is located at the broader line of Rajshahi division, also near the Bangladesh-India international border. From these two districts, 10 subdistricts have been chosen for the study, and they are Nawabganj Sadar, Shibganj, Natore Sadar, Singra, Gurudaspur, Lalpur, Bagatipara, Nachole, Bholahat, and Goamstapur. Among them, Singra, Natore Sadar, Bagatipara, Gurudaspur, and Lalpur are in Natore district, which latitude and longitude are 24.4124° N, 88.9756° E (Latlonginfo, 2023), and Shibganj, Nachole, Gomastapur, Nababganj Sadar, and Bholahat are in Chapai Nababganj district, which are in 24.7413°N, 88.2912°E (LATITUDE, 2025). These sub-districts are chosen because of their geological location, and these sub-districts are surrounded by multiple rivers like Padma, Narod, Atrai etc, The projected coordinate system used for this study is WGS_1984_UTM_Zone_45N, which is suitable for Bangladesh (ESRI, 1999)

Figure 1: Study Area

3 Materials and Methods

The inexpensive part for a better knowledge of numerous components and elements related to the research studies is the use of qualitative and quantitative approaches. (Tabassum et al.)

3.1 Data collection

For the study, the BBS 2011 and BBS 2021 data have been used for exposure and capital data collection. The BBS data has been collected from the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics. Five Capitals of UNDP Sustainable Livelihood Framework (SLF) has been used for the study because these capitals are strategy to protect livelihoods, (i.e., physical capital, financial capital, human capital, natural capital, and social capital) and focuses on the assets or capitals to bring about an initial assessment and future prognosis of communities before and after UNDP program interventions (Elizondo, 2015). The indicators for each capital are shown in Table 1. For Hazard, water level data has been collected from the Bangladesh Water Development Board (BWDB). Shapefiles of the sub-districts are produced by using Landsat 8 images.

Table 1: Capital Indicators

Capital	Parameters
Physical	Number of existing Flood Camp/Shelter
Natural	Number of river flows
Financial	Average wage rate of agriculture
Social	Number of cooperative societies
Human	Literacy Rate (7+)

3.2 Hazard Assessment

A total of 6 river water level data have been used for hazard calculation. A thumb rule has been used here to calculate the water level of each district, shown in equation (1). The (+) sign is used when the targeted location's elevation is less than the known river location. The (-) sign is used when the targeted location's elevation is greater than the known river location. The 2-5cm/km water level varies according to the thumb rule, where 5cm or 0.05m is considered, assuming the tidal river condition.

$$\text{Water level of the targeted location} = \text{known river recorded water level} \pm (\text{distance between targeted location and known river location in km} \times 0.05) \quad (1)$$

3.3 Vulnerability and Risk Assessment

The equation for risk (R) can be expressed as a non-linear combination of exposure (E), vulnerability(V), and hazard (H) (Wisner et al., 2003)

$$R = E \times H \times V \quad (2)$$

People, property, systems, or other elements present in hazard zones are thereby subject to potential losses, and these elements are considered as Exposure. The basic equation of the capital approach has been shown in equation (3). (Haque et al., 2024) The total capital of the community has been calculated by the sum of all the capitals.

$$\text{Vulnerability} = 1 - \text{Total capital of the community} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Risk} = \text{Hazard} * \text{Exposure} * (1 - \text{Total Capital of the Community}) \quad (4)$$

For a multi-parameter and multi-location environment, the methodology is shown in Figure 2. Weights are assigned by using expert opinions, where the experts are mainly government officials. Equations (5)-(7) are used to calculate the normalized and the weighted normalized values of the selected indicators.

Figure 2:Steps for a multi-parameter and multi-location environment

$$Normalized\ Value = \frac{1 + \frac{(100-1) \cdot (Value - Minimum\ Value)}{(Maximum\ Value - Minimum\ Value)}}{100} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{Weight_{Parameter}(Location_{unknown\ weight})}{Weight_{Parameter}(Location_{known\ weight})} = \frac{X \cdot Normalized\ Parameter\ Value_{Location_{unknown\ Weight}}}{Maximum\ Normalized\ Parameter\ Value_{Location_{known\ Weight}}} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{Weighted\ Normalized\ Value_{Parameter}(Location_{unknown\ weight})}{Weight_{Parameter}(Location_{known\ weight})} = \frac{X \cdot (Normalized\ Parameter\ Value_{Location_{unknown\ Weight}})^2}{Maximum\ Normalized\ Parameter\ Value_{Location_{known\ Weight}}} \quad (7)$$

4 Results

As mentioned earlier, risk is a non-linear combination of hazard, exposure, and vulnerability. According to the calculation, Shibganj has the highest risk scores of being affected by floods, with the maximum score of 0.5. On the other hand, Singra has the lowest flood-affected hazard score, which is 0.00177. From the hazard map in Figure 3, the dark shades forecast the areas that are susceptible to flooding, whereas lighter shades represent areas that are less susceptible during floods.

Figure 3: Hazard Map of 10 sub-districts

For vulnerability and risk, it has been observed that Gomastapur is the most vulnerable among the 10 subdistricts of Rajshahi division to flood with a vulnerability score of 0.98697 where Natore Sadar is less vulnerable to flood with a vulnerability score of 0.31012 and same as Figure 3, a vulnerability map has been shown in Figure 4 (a) where the darker shades are representing higher vulnerable sub-districts and lighter ones are representing lower vulnerable sub-districts as same thing happens for the risk assessment map in Figure 5(a). From the map, it has been seen that Shibganj, which has been in the highest hazard zone by hazard score (water level), is also in the highest risk zone, and it obtains a risk value of 0.283. After that, Nawabganj Sadar has been the second-highest risk zone with a risk score of 0.17335. Among these 10 sub-districts, Lalpur has the lowest risk score, which is 0.00000781689. For the policy makers, a trial has been done for Shibganj to see the shifting of risk, if the capital values are improved. All the capitals expect natural capital has been increased arbitrary 50% of their current stats. For natural capital, it's practically not feasible to change the number of rivers within a subdistrict. So, in this new scenario, it has been seen in Figure 5(b) that Shibganj, which is in a very high-risk zone considering flood, has now moved to second place and Nawabganj Sadar, whose risk score is 0.1748, has now the highest risk zone to flood. But for vulnerability, though the values have been changed, all zones remain the same as previous, except Shibganj, which has now moved from a highly vulnerable area to a low vulnerable area shown in Figure 4(b). But

hazard and exposure all scores remain the same as the previous. Therefore, it has been clear that one indicator change can be reasonable for shifting risk. Also, an arbitrary change in values can pose an effect (Figure 6); sometimes it may bring good sight for the targeted district, on the other hand, it can be negative for other sub-districts also, as we see in the context of Shibganj and Nawabganj Sadar. Now, to increase capital, one example can be given that is for the increase of literacy rate, more schools have to be built and qualified. ones are needed to be involved in.

Figure 4: Vulnerability map((a): BBS value, (b) Arbitrary Trial value)

Figure 5: Risk Mapping of 10-Sub districts (a): BBS value, (b) Arbitrary Trial value

Figure 6: Trend of Risk Change in the targeted district

5 Discussion and Conclusion

This study has demonstrated the strength of the Capital Approach in risk assessment. The study is considered comprehensive as it integrates hydrological data with the socio-economic data to calculate risk and how this risk is affected differently due to variations in the availability of capital. In this study, it is found that the presence and distribution of capitals at the sub-district level (relatively a smaller scale compared to the larger Division level) could significantly change the severity of the flood impact measured by risk. It is found that the Shibganj sub-district is located in the highest flood hazard zone, and it has shown a very high vulnerability score, but in terms of risk score, it is in a higher risk zone after Shibganj due to its limited capital. In order to lower vulnerability and risk, the study also shows how the Capital Approach practically shows the precise areas where investments can be made for capital enhancement, such as social structure, flood shelters, and literacy. Findings from the study suggest that an improvement in capital, especially human and social capital, will actually help to reduce vulnerability and change the distribution of risk and thus result in the formation of resilient communities. The outcome points to the significance of formulating interventions that address particular challenges faced by flood-prone sub-districts, e.g., education and social cohesion, infrastructure, and equitable access to resources. The study advocates a paradigm shift in disaster management approaches, favoring the incorporation of capital-based approaches into policies to alleviate vulnerability and foster long-term resilience against floods. Also, from the arbitrary trial it has been seen that increasing capital won't change the hazard score but can change the risk score. Future studies could explore the effects of other types of capital that are not included in the UNDP Sustainable Livelihood Framework but need to be considered in terms of Bangladesh, such as cultural and political capital.

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